

**THE ROLE OF INTEGRATING MARTIAL ARTS INTO
LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION FOR THE
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF
CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION**

Ionuț Marian GHEORGHIAN¹

Elena Mihaela CUCEANU²

Liliana Niculina MIHĂILESCU³

Răzvan Liviu PETRE⁴

^{1,2,3} National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest,
Pitești University Centre

⁴ National University of Physical Education and Sport, Bucharest, Romania.

Abstract

Through a systematic review of the existing literature, this article aims to analyse the role, importance, and benefits of martial arts in contemporary educational programmes.

Based on the premises of education focused on sustainable development, the study highlights the importance of martial arts within school curricula through an analysis of good practices from other countries, where various sports disciplines specific to martial arts are included either as compulsory or optional subjects within physical education programmes.

In the context of contemporary society, in which the level of aggression in schools has become increasingly concerning, the practice of martial arts sports disciplines may represent an effective means through which this phenomenon can be prevented and addressed.

In recent years, the phenomenon of bullying has attracted the attention of a growing number of specialists from various fields (psychology, pedagogy, as well as sport science and physical education), who have sought to identify its causes and effects, as well as different methods of prevention and reduction.

From the documentary sources studied, in addition to psycho-physical, social, and spiritual benefits, the educational dimension of martial arts is also emphasised, as it contributes to the process of students' formation and development, facilitating their integration into society. Thus, scientific arguments are presented in support of the idea that martial arts represent a valuable and innovative tool for the sustainability of the educational process.

Keywords: martial arts, sustainable education, personal development, extracurricular activities, bullying.

Introduction

In contemporary society, education has become a key tool for shaping socially responsible citizens who are capable of making balanced decisions regarding the educational process. Despite this, Ukamaka (2024) notes that in a democratic and sustainable society, education does not receive sufficient attention, and the implementation of a school programme focused on

sustainability requires a set of skills and knowledge that teachers do not always possess.

In the same vein, Clark (2022) argues that sustainable development is a tool through which the present and future sustainability of education can be ensured.

Ukamaka (2024) discusses three strategies that can be applied to integrate sustainability into the educational curriculum, namely:

- intercurricular integration – aimed at extending sustainability across multiple subjects to “address the challenges of the current school curriculum”;
- project-based learning – through this strategy, the transition from theoretical learning to practical learning experiences is facilitated;
- community partnerships – to identify solutions to various sustainability-related issues within a local context.

Considering these strategies, martial arts may constitute a solution for integrating sustainability into the educational curriculum, as “teaching strategies represent systems of methods, procedures, learning resources and forms of organising students’ activities, aimed at constructing learning experiences, developing competences and rationalising the instructional–educational process” (Papuc & Bocoş, 2017).

In support of this idea, Lohmann, Tittlbach and Steinbauer (2024) conducted a conceptual article through which it was highlighted that sport and physical activities can be integrated into the sustainable development of education, presenting solid evidence regarding the contribution made to practitioners in the development of physical and mental health.

Objectives

The purpose of our research is to highlight the contribution of introducing martial arts into the educational curriculum, emphasising the role of these in the harmonious formation of students, correlated with the improvement of school

performance, as well as with the reduction of students' aggressive behaviours, in all their forms. The integration of disciplines specific to martial arts (Judo, Karate, Kempo, Ju-Jitsu, Taekwondo, etc.) into the school environment can support the sustainability of contemporary education, through the benefits provided, such as the psycho-physical development of practitioners, the increase of self-confidence, adaptation in different situations, social inclusion, and more.

Thus, the objectives of this research focus on the relationship between martial arts, education, and sustainable development, as well as the prevention and reduction of aggressive behaviour within the educational system. Consequently, the following objectives have been established:

1. To analyse the impact of martial arts-specific sports disciplines on student development and identify possible ways of integrating them into the school environment.
2. To highlight the role of martial arts in preventing aggressive behaviours, considering the phenomenon of school violence – manifested in all its forms – which, regrettably, has grown considerably in contemporary society.
3. To reduce problems of aggression in schools through the promotion and implementation of martial arts sports disciplines within the school curriculum.

Materials and Methods

For this article, we started with the following keywords: “martial arts,” “sustainable education,” “bullying,” “aggressiveness,” and “personal development.” Based on these terms, an extensive search was conducted across

various academic platforms, in national and international scientific journals, as well as in relevant specialised studies, official reports, and courses. The studies included and analysed in this article were those published in the last six years, in order to emphasise recent developments in research within fields such as education, psychology, and martial arts.

For a broader understanding and greater clarity of the research process carried out, we will systematically present the criteria considered for the inclusion and exclusion of the analysed articles, as well as the number of articles at each stage of the study, using a Prisma flow diagram.

Figure 1. Prisma diagram of the study identification process through databases and registers

Results

1.1. Integration of Martial Arts in Lower Secondary Education

The number of studies focusing on the implementation of martial arts in the lower secondary education system is relatively limited. In this regard, the research direction will be expanded by reporting and analysing a larger number of sports disciplines specific to martial arts, such as Karate, Judo, Taekwondo, Kempo and Pencak Silat.

Martial arts, through their variety of styles, contribute to the development of moral qualities and the formation of a balanced character, and their consistent practice from an early age facilitates the development of social behaviour and the adoption of a well-organised and healthy lifestyle (Balazs, 2021).

A key study relevant to this subchapter is that conducted by Pinto-Escalona et al. (2021), which evaluated the effects of a one-year intervention based on a Karate programme (“Mind and Movement”) on a sample of 721 children aged 7–8 years from 20 schools across 5 European countries. This research analysed students’ academic performance, psychosocial functioning, and physical condition. The results indicated that integrating a Karate programme into physical education classes can bring modest benefits to children.

Complementing this study, Pinto-Escalona et al. (2022) conducted an additional analysis using the same programme described previously, noting that this time a sample of 388 children was considered. The measurement instruments used were academic performance (average grade) and the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (completed by the subjects’ parents), which had also been employed in the previous study. Following the application of these tools,

the authors observed that the Karate programme implemented in schools did not have a uniform effect on all participants; however, they highlighted improvements in children with behavioural and emotional difficulties.

Another noteworthy intervention was conducted through the Kick-Smart programme, in which Burt, Riley, Parkes & Eather (2021) carried out a randomised feasibility study in a primary school in Australia. This programme aimed to integrate basic martial arts training into the school curriculum, in conjunction with physical education and elements of mathematics, over a six-week period.

Two 60-minute sessions per week were delivered to a sample of 46 children aged 9–11 years, randomly assigned to two groups. The intervention group participated in the Kick-Smart programme during school physical education lessons, while the control group continued with traditional physical education classes. Following this intervention, the results confirmed that the programme is feasible for implementation in the educational setting, with significant effects observed for the intervention group on physical fitness and mathematics performance.

Additionally, this programme was appreciated for the level of enjoyment and the perceived benefits reported by both students and teachers. Regarding the study's limitations, the authors noted the small sample size and emphasised the need for studies involving larger samples to confirm and strengthen the reported results.

In an effort to demonstrate that martial arts promote adaptation to the school environment and psychological well-being among lower secondary students, Moore, Dudley & Woodcock (2023) conducted a randomised controlled study with a sample of 283 students, with a mean age of 12.5 years, implementing a martial arts-based intervention limited to 10 sessions of 60 minutes each.

The intervention consisted of psychoeducational discussions, warm-up and stretching exercises, technical exercises specific to martial arts disciplines, adapted kumite (sparring) activities, and meditation techniques focused on breathing.

The results indicated that the intervention group showed improvements in self-efficacy compared with the control group. The authors emphasise the importance of such interventions in the school setting as a means of psychosocial support and promoting students' mental well-being.

1.2. Aggressive Behaviour in the School Environment

The specialised literature defines aggressiveness as hostile and destructive behaviour directed towards others or even oneself (Olaru, 2022). According to Bonea (2019), the term aggressiveness, in the school context, is defined as deviant behaviour, manifested in various forms and with differing intensities.

In this regard, Georgescu and Guțu (2024) highlight that school aggressiveness is strongly influenced by the relational atmosphere in the classroom, the quality of interactions among students, and the extent to which the psychological climate either supports or, conversely, amplifies tensions and disruptive behaviours.

In recent literature, the term aggressiveness is often associated with bullying, which represents a specific and repetitive form of aggression. According to UNESCO (2023), school bullying is “a harmful social process characterised by a power imbalance determined by social and institutional norms, manifested through unwanted behaviours that cause physical, social, or emotional harm to the targeted individuals.” The organisation recommends a holistic approach to the phenomenon, in which prevention plays a central role, focusing not only on targeted interventions following incidents but, more importantly, on

building a safe, inclusive school environment governed by rules that systematically discourage aggressive behaviours and victimisation.

Beyond its concrete forms, bullying is influenced by a range of psychological, relational, and environmental factors that contribute to the emergence and persistence of such behaviour. In this context, preventing this phenomenon requires an integrated approach, which includes a safe, cohesive, and predictable educational setting.

Based on the review of several studies and specialised literature addressing bullying, Gavrilesco & Merloiu (2021), Bîţca (2024), Ahmed, Metwaly, Elbeh, Galal & Shaaban (2022), Grecu (2020), and Georgescu (2024), the main factors contributing to the manifestation of aggressive behaviours in the school environment, as well as some strategies for preventing this phenomenon, have been identified and synthesised in the figure below. This representation is concise, as the specialised literature and numerous studies on this topic describe a much more complex range of factors and possible interventions to reduce and halt this phenomenon. Therefore, in the following figure, the main factors that influence school aggressiveness are highlighted in an accessible and easy-to-follow manner, as well as certain prevention directions suggested by specialists.

Figure 2. Factors Influencing School Aggressio

1.3. Reducing Aggressiveness in the Educational System through the Implementation of Martial Arts

Starting from the premise that martial arts can positively influence aggressive behaviour in the school context, many researchers have sought to highlight their benefits in developing self-control, discipline, and respect for others.

In this regard, Lindell-Postigo et al. (2023) conducted a study involving a group of 139 participants, with a mean age of approximately 12.7 years, to analyse the effects of a Judo training programme on aggressive behaviour, emotional intelligence, self-concept, and the motivational climate. A questionnaire-based research instrument was applied before and after the intervention to measure these variables.

The results indicated that the Judo training intervention reduced the participants' aggressive behaviours, while moderate increases were observed in emotional intelligence and self-concept. One of the authors' conclusions suggests that Judo training can be incorporated into the educational system to help reduce aggressive behaviours among students with such issues.

Complementing the previous study, Xu, Yan, Li, Zhang, G. & Zhang, Y. (2023) conducted research using psychological questionnaires to compare levels of self-control, aggressiveness, and bullying between martial arts practitioners and non-athletes. The study involved 401 martial arts practitioners and 374 children who did not practice such disciplines, with a mean age of 13.5 years.

The results confirmed that martial arts practitioners exhibited lower aggressive behaviour compared with non-athletes. Additionally, it was observed that practising martial arts contributes to improving self-control. As methods for preventing aggressive behaviour in primary and secondary schools, the authors suggest implementing martial arts-specific exercises during physical education classes and encouraging students to engage in such activities regularly.

Two other studies evaluating the influence of martial arts practice on children under 14 years old regarding self-control, aggressiveness, and bullying support the hypotheses of our research, namely that martial arts, beyond their psycho-physical component, also include an educational and behavioural dimension.

Thus, Luo, Ma, Hu & Zhao (2025) conducted a study focused on a systematic review and meta-analysis, analysing 16 randomized controlled clinical studies. The results indicated that programmes incorporating martial arts can improve students' prosocial behaviour and, at the same time, reduce levels of aggressive behaviour.

The other study included 775 adolescents and focused on analysing the practice of martial arts in controlling aggressive behaviours. The research involved administering and analysing questionnaires that assessed levels of self-control, aggressiveness, and adolescents' involvement in bullying behaviours. The results confirmed that martial arts practitioners displayed higher levels of self-control and lower levels of aggressiveness and bullying compared with adolescents who did not practise such sports disciplines.

In contrast to the previously presented studies, another study conducted by Nur'aini, Alif & Rukmana (2024) indicated higher levels of hostile aggressiveness among martial arts practitioners aged 10 to 12 years compared with children who do not practise martial arts. This research examined three martial arts styles: Taekwondo, Pencak Silat, and Karate, and applied the Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire, which measures physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, and hostility, on a sample of 118 children. The increase in hostility was particularly observed among participants practising Pencak Silat.

In this regard, the authors suggest that the level of aggressiveness among martial arts athletes may vary depending on age, the type of martial arts practiced, and the training methods used during sessions. Regarding the other two sports disciplines analysed in the study, the results indicated a moderate level of

aggressiveness compared with non-practising children.

In conclusion, we highlight the study conducted by Costea, Moraru & Cobzeanu (2025) on 254 Romanian adolescents, which shows that Kempo practitioners report lower levels of offline victimisation compared with non-practitioners, indicating that martial arts can reduce students' exposure to bullying, though not necessarily the psychological effects of victimisation.

Discussion

Considering the studies discussed, we can confirm a positive answer to the question “can martial arts represent an effective tool within the educational system, contributing both to the sustainable development of education and to the reduction and prevention of various aggressive behaviours in the school environment?”.

We found that some specialists (Nur'aini et al., 2024) present concrete evidence, based on scientific research, through which they highlight the fact that the impact of certain sports disciplines specific to martial arts on practitioners' aggressiveness is not uniform, being influenced by numerous factors. Thus, within training sessions, special attention must be given to the educational and behavioural dimension, correlated with psycho-physical preparation appropriate to the age and level of training of each practitioner.

Essentially, not only certain sports disciplines can influence the level of aggressiveness of practitioners, but also the way in which they are taught within the instructional–educational process. In the current context, the implementation of playful methods within martial arts training is considered, especially for the age level represented by lower secondary education, thus contributing to the strengthening of social relationships, the reduction of anxiety and the self-control of children (Lindell-Postigo et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2023).

The analysed studies, which focused on disciplines such as Karate, Judo, Taekwondo, and Kempo, demonstrated positive effects on students' social

adaptation, self-control, and self-efficacy, values considered essential in the formation of responsible and balanced students. These results confirm that martial arts can be integrated into various sustainable educational strategies, a point further supported by Burt et al. (2021) through the implementation of the Kick-Smart programme, previously discussed in this article.

The results, which indicated improvements in self-control, frustration tolerance, and resilience to victimisation, can significantly reduce students' involvement in aggressive behaviours.

In some countries, (Japan, South Korea, Brazil, and more) martial arts are included in the educational system, either as compulsory subjects or as optional disciplines within physical education programmes. Based on this, the Romanian educational system could implement martial arts disciplines as an optional subject or as an extracurricular activity, thereby enhancing the educational process, strengthening the relationship between school and society, and preventing and reducing aggressive behaviours among students.

The limitations of this study stem from the small number of studies focusing on children of lower secondary school age, which required expanding the search to include multiple sports disciplines, as well as the relatively short duration of certain programmes that included martial arts. This may have influenced the depth of discussions and conclusions. More detailed research is needed, involving larger student samples, rigorous methodologies, and well-controlled experimental designs. In the future, we will aim to expand existing research relevant to the age group discussed by accessing a broader range of academic databases, journals, and national and international publications.

Conclusions

1. Recent studies highlight the importance of martial arts disciplines in the sustainable development of contemporary education, providing numerous benefits to practitioners, including physical, psychological, social, and

emotional advantages.

2. The analysed studies demonstrate that practising martial arts is an effective strategy for preventing and reducing aggressive behaviours as well as bullying. Their conclusions indicate that students involved in sports programmes incorporating martial arts exhibit lower levels of aggressiveness, increased frustration tolerance, and greater resilience to victimisation.
3. The proliferation of bullying in schools underscores the need for educational interventions. Practising martial arts as a mass-participation sport has proven to be a viable and complementary solution, with a strong positive impact on the psychosocial climate of the student community.

References

- Ahmed, G. K., Metwaly, N. A., Elbeh, K., Galal, M. S., & Shaaban, I. (2022). Risk factors of school bullying and its relationship with psychiatric comorbidities: A literature review. *Egyptian Journal of Neurology, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery*, 58(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41983-022-00449-x>
- Balazs, E. (2021). *Rolul artelor marțiale în dezvoltarea fizică armonioasă a elevilor în cadrul palatului copiilor*. Arad: Editura Școala Vremii. Retrieved from: <https://palatulcopiilorarad.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Rolul-artelor-martialeindezvoltarea-fizica-armonioasa-pdf.pdf>
- Bîțca, L. (2023). Rezultanta psihologică în diminuarea bullyingului la preadolescenți. *Probleme și soluții în știința contemporană*. 149–155. <https://doi.org/10.46727/c.01-02-12-2023.p149-155>
- Bonea, G. V. (2019). Agresivitatea și violența în școlile din România: bullying și mobbing. *Calitatea Vieții*, 30(1), 59–75. Retrieved from: <https://revistacalitateavietii.ro/journal/article/view/148>
- Burt, L. D., Riley, N., Parkes, R. J., Eather, N. (2021). The Kick-Smart Program: A Randomized Feasibility Trial Evaluating the Feasibility and Efficacy of a Primary-School-Based Martial Arts Program Integrating Mathematics, Physical Fitness and Well-Being. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*. 9(3), 47-57. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v9i3.5142>
- Clark, K. R. (2022). Education for sustainable development, curriculum reform and implications for teacher education in a small Island developing state. *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*. 13(1), 145-153. DOI: 10.2478/dcse-2022-0011
- Costea, I., Moraru, C.-E., & Cobzeanu, A. (2025). Kicking back

- against bullying: Social media, psychological distress, and the moderating role of Kempo training among Romanian adolescents. *International Journal of Social and Educational Innovation*, 12(23), 1–18. Retrieved from:
<https://www.journals.aseiacademic.org/index.php/ijsei/article/download/493/374>
- Gavrilescu, A. S., Merloiu, F. (2021). Fenomenul de bullying în școlile din România. *New Trends in Psychology*, 3(2).
<https://dj.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/NTP/article/view/1408>
- Georgescu, I. C. (2024). Prevenirea și diminuarea comportamentului agresiv de tip bullying: cadrul teoretic și praxiologic. *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae*, 9(169), 165–170. [https://doi.org/10.59295/sum9\(169\)2024_24](https://doi.org/10.59295/sum9(169)2024_24)
- Georgescu, C. I., Guțu, V. (2024). Climatul psihologic al clasei – factor de prevenire și reducere a agresivității școlare. *Studia Universitatis Moldaviae. Seria Științe ale Educației*, 5(175), 78–84. [https://doi.org/10.59295/sum5\(175\)2024_11](https://doi.org/10.59295/sum5(175)2024_11)
- Greco, E. R. (2020). *Bullying în mediile educaționale: De la bullying la suicid* (Teză de doctorat, Universitatea din Craiova, Facultatea de Științe Sociale, Școala Doctorală de Științe Sociale și Umaniste). Retrieved from: <https://rei.gov.ro/teze-doctorat>
- Lindell-Postigo, D., Zurita-Ortega, F., Melguizo-Ibáñez, E., González-Valero, G., Ortiz-Franco, M., Ubago-Jiménez, J. L. (2023) Effectiveness of a Judo Intervention Programme on the Psychosocial Area in Secondary School Education Students. *Sports*, 11, 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports11080140>
- Lohmann, J., Tittlbach, S., Steinbauer, M. J. (2024). Sustainable development in sport and physical activity – perspectives and

- challenges. *German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research*. 54, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12662-023-00938-y>
- Luo, Q., Ma, X., Hu, G., Zhao, B. (2025). Effect of Martial Arts Exercise on Children's Prosocial and Aggressive Behaviors: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Adolescent Research Review*. DOI:[10.1007/s40894-025-00271-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40894-025-00271-5)
- Moore, B., Dudley, D., Woodcock, S. (2023). The Effects of a Martial Arts-Based Intervention on Secondary School Students' Self-Efficacy: A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Philosophies*. 8(3), 43. <https://doi.org/10.3390/philosophies8030043>
- Nur'aini, F. H., Alif, M. N., Rukmana, A. (2024). Aggressiveness level of martial arts participants in children. *Journal of Physical Education, Sport, Health and Recreation*, 13(3), 436-443. DOI: [10.15294/peshr.v13i3.9533](https://doi.org/10.15294/peshr.v13i3.9533)
- Olaru, A. D. (2022). *Ghid pentru prevenirea și combaterea violenței în școli* (Proiect „Educație de calitate și management eficient pentru o școală de succes”). Școala Gimnazială „Nicolae Titulescu”, Călărași. Retrieved from: <https://www.isj-cl.ro/images/Curriculum/Ghid%20pentru%20prevenirea%20si%20combaterea%20violentei%20in%20scoli.pdf>
- Papuc, I., Bogoș, M. (2017). *Psihopedagogie. Suporturi pentru formarea inițială și continuă*. Editura Cartea Românească Educațională
- Pinto-Escalona, T., Valenzuela, P. L., Martin-Loeches, M., Martinez-de-Quel, O. (2022). Individual responsiveness to a school-based karate intervention: an ancillary analysis of a randomized controlled trial. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine and Science in Sports*. 32(8), 1249-1257. DOI: [10.1111/sms.14167](https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.14167)
- Pinto-Escalona, T., Gobbi, E., Valenzuela, P. L., Bennett, S. J., Aschieri, P., Martin-Loeches, M., Paoli, A., Martinez-de-Quel,

- O. (2021). Effects of a school-based karate intervention on academic achievement, psychosocial functioning, and physical fitness: a multi-country cluster randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2021.10.006>
- UNESCO. (2023). *Defining school bullying and its implications for education, teachers and learners*. Retrieved from: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/defining-school-bullying-and-its-implications-education-teachers-and-learners>
- Ukamaka, E. J. (2024). Education for sustainable development: Integrating sustainability into curricula. *Research Output Journal of Arts and Management*. 3(3), 53-57. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383556278_Education_for_Sustainable_Development_Integrating_Sustainability_into_Curricula
- Xu, T., Li, H., Yan, Z., Zhang, G. (2022). The effects of self-control on bullying behaviour among martial arts practicing adolescents: based on the analyses of multiple mediation effects. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 22(4), 1-14. DOI:[10.1080/1612197X.2022.2116470](https://doi.org/10.1080/1612197X.2022.2116470)
- Xu, T., Yan, Z., Li, H., Zhang, G., Zhang, Y. (2023). Self-control, aggression and bullying of martial arts practitioners and non-martial arts practitioners: A comparative study and factor analysis. *Archives of Budo*, 19, 119-128. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375496344_Self

-

control aggression and bullying of martial arts practitioners and non-martial arts practitioners A comparative study and factor analysis